

COMPLICATIONS AFTER LIVER RESECTIONS- POST-RESECTION LIVER FAILURE**Dimitar Rusenov**Dr., MD., *Clinic of Liver-biliary,**Pancreatic and General Surgery Acibadem City Clinic Tokuda Hospital EAD**Bul. „H. Vaptsarov ”51 B Sofia 1408***Abstract**

Liver surgery is historically one of the "youngest" areas in abdominal surgery, but at the same time it marks very rapid progress and continuous development, which continues even today.

Development of liver resection surgery has been linked to a parenchymal dissection techniques and reliable hemostasis and biliostasis,

The International Study Group of Liver Surgery (ISGLS) provides definitions and criteria for The assessment of Specific pastresection complications.

Keywords: liver resections, complications after liver resections, liver failure.

Introduction:

Prerequisites for the rapid development of liver resection surgery are the established anatomical knowledge of segmental hepatic anatomy, the improvement of techniques for parenchymal dissection and definitive hemo- and biliostasis, the improvement of hepatoprotection methods and means, the development of anesthesia and resuscitation care for operated patients.

Objective:

Determination of a possible prognostic role of the type of liver resection (anatomic or atypical) for the risk of occurrence, frequency and severity of postoperative specific complications- liver failure.

Materials and methods:

For the period from January, 2007 - March, 2018 in Clinic of liver, biliary pancreatic and general surgery, Acibadem City Clinic Tokuda Hospital ,1021 interventions were performed on the liver:

Cases of intervention other than liver resection by definition were excluded ISGLS, "removal of part of the liver parenchyma due to involvement by a disease process or traumatic injury resulting in devitalization of the parenchyma".

Thus, the study did not find the cases of:

- hepatotomy;

- cystotomies and cyst resections, practically without removal of functioning or pathologically altered liver parenchyma;

-liver biopsies, alcoholization of tumors. liver biopsies, alcoholization of tumors;

- interruption of trunk branches of the hepatic artery and/or portal vein with the aim of hypoperfusion of a given area (segments, lobe);

- suture of the liver in trauma;

Thus, a total of 852 cases of liver resections were included in the series

Results:

In modern liver resection surgery, acute liver failure is a major cause of fatal outcome. In our study, we found signs of liver failure in 17 patients, of whom 10 were after Anatomic liver resection, as a stand-alone procedure (2.6%) or as part of multivisceral resection (6.1%) compared to Atypical liver resection (0.5% as stand-alone and 1.5% in multivisceral resections) (Table 1).

Our criteria for the occurrence of acute liver failure were based on the definition of ISGLS (2011) - "disturbance in the synthetic, excretory and detoxification function of the liver manifested by an increase in INR and hyperbilirubinemia recorded on or after the 5th postoperative day this'.

Table 1.

Incidence of post-resection acute liver failure after Anatomic and Atypical liver resections						
Another operation	acute liver failure	Statistics	Anatomic resection	Atypical resection	Total	P
No	No	N	113	218	331	0,122
		%	97,4%	99,5%	98,8%	
	Yes	N	3	1	4	
		%	2,6%	,5%	1,2%	
Yes	No	N	107	398	505	0,011
		%	93,9%	98,5%	97,5%	
	Yes	N	7	6	13	
		%	6,1%	1,5%	2,5%	

All patients after liver resection received a hepatoprotector as an element of resuscitation therapy, as well as Human albumin 20%, 100ml and a proton pump inhibitor.

In 4 patients, we found acute liver failure as Grade A, not requiring a change in the therapeutic scheme.

The remaining 13 cases had more severe violations. Nine of them were Grade B, which necessitated a change in resuscitation therapy. In 4 patients, hemofiltration was included as an invasive procedure (Grade C). 5 of the 13 patients with Grade B and C were excited, and in all five we reported the "50-50 criteria" of Balzan and Belghiti: the "intersection" of the prothrombin index <50% and serum bilirubin >50 µmol/L on the 5th postoperative day', i.e. these criteria indeed proved to be an early and accurate predictor of mortality.

Discussion:

Five patients in our series developed acute liver failure, leading to a fatal outcome. Post-resection hemorrhage Grade B was registered in two of them, and Grade C in two. Hemorrhage with tissue and organ hypoperfusion, as well as liver hypoperfusion is a prerequisite for hepatocellular failure with a negative impact on the final result.

We registered two other exits after internal bilirubin, peritonitis, sepsis and MODS, which necessitated reoperation

Conclusion:

Liver resection surgery should be performed in centers with sufficient experience in this field, working according to established standards and algorithms.

Acute liver failure is a typical specific post-resection complication after anatomic liver resections -

as a stand-alone procedure and as part of a multivisceral resection,

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